

LETTER TO THE EDITOR

Malayan Pangolins: The missing piece to the puzzle of COVID-19

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The novel beta coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, which was first detected in the Wuhan seafood market of China has viciously spread its roots across 216 countries. Up until the date of this writing (3:47 pm CEST, 7 June 2020), it has infected 6,799,713 people and caused 397,388 deaths globally. [1] SARS-CoV-2 spreads from one person to another, particularly when the latter comes in close contact with an infected patient or is exposed to respiratory droplets produced by coughing or sneezing. These droplets enter the body through the oral cavity, nasal cavity, uncovered eyes, and exposed mucous membrane. [2] In addition to this, the Japanese Association for Infectious Disease has suggested the high possibility of microdroplets transmission of COVID-19. [3] The effortless mode of transmission of COVID-19 has contributed extensively to its spread globally, to the extent our routine life has been brought to a halt, in wait for a potential solution to this disease.

Bats have been known as the natural reservoir of members of the Coronavirus family, including SARS-CoV-2. [4] However, a fact, which has not yet been profoundly explored, is the implication of an intermediate host in the spread of the 7th human coronavirus. Surprisingly, bats were not being sold at the Wuhan seafood market, yet it was where SARS-CoV-2 saw the light of day. [5] This is highly suggestive of the presence of an intermediate host, possibly the Malayan pangolin.

Figure 1: Malayan Pangolins: Are they intermediate hosts?

Source: Yi et al. Int J Biol Sci 2020. [6]

The Malayan Pangolin or *Manis javanica* belongs to one out of the eight known species of pangolins globally. Owing to their great demand for consumption and use in

traditional medicine, pangolins have been poached and trafficked more than any other mammal worldwide, such that today they are on the brink of extinction. Research using metagenomics techniques revealed a wide range of viruses, which were identified in dead Malayan pangolins. Moreover, Sendai virus and Coronavirus had predominance over the other viral species found in the dead pangolins. On further research, different types of SARS-CoV were also identified, suggesting that Malayan pangolins could be a potential host in the spread of SARS-CoV. Interestingly, the death of these pangolins has also been related to these coronavirus species. [7]

As COVID-19 continues to exert its virulent impact globally, more research has been carried out on Malayan pangolins and its relationship with SARS-CoV-2. As per a study, the genomic analysis of specimens obtained from Malayan pangolins revealed the presence of viruses belonging to 2 sub-genera of SARS-CoV-2 related viruses [8]. Moreover, a similarity of 85.5-92.4% to that of SARS-CoV-2 was also identified upon genomic sequencing. [8] This is highly indicative that Malayan pangolins could be potential intermediate hosts for COVID-19. The role played by Malayan Pangolins in the transmission of COVID-19, and other Coronaviruses pathogenic to humans requires increased research so that a more definitive link can be established between the two.

Keywords

Coronavirus, Malayan, pangolins, SARS-CoV-2, spread, transmission

Abbreviations

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)

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